

carlowitz-planspiel

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Keywords

Sustainability sciences, sustainability management, forestry sciences, climate change, sustainability goals

Figure 1. *Photographic documentation of the **Carlowitz-Planspiel** simulation game in educational settings. Images show gameplay materials, participant interaction, and facilitation contexts—photographs used for illustrative purposes only.*

Introduction

The aim of the game **Carlowitz-Planspiel – growing with trees** is to handle wood skillfully and with a future-oriented perspective: cultivating trees in a value-enhancing way, brokering and trading wood in a tailored manner, and using wood to create meaningful benefits. The simulation is based on Carlowitz's guiding principle of sustainability and models economic decisions related to the cultivation, trade, and use of wood. Learning objectives include understanding selected mechanisms of sustainable forestry and timber management, as well as developing a sense of individual responsibility from the perspectives of forest managers and customers.

In its design, the approach integrates market- and competition-based approaches, as well as transformative approaches to strong sustainability, and is guided by scenarios and events. Action-oriented and participant-centered principles lead to a combined didactic approach that integrates haptic-analog and digital elements, enabling varied perspectives and promoting self-reflection. A debriefing phase for reflective critique concludes the game rounds.

The Carlowitz-Planspiel aims to convey knowledge, foster action competence, and encourage sustainable behavioral change in real life. It combines round-based gameplay with transformative learning objectives, employs methodological approaches from simulation-game didactics, and focuses on real-life problem situations to enable direct transfer of learning.

www.carlowitz-planspiel.de

Facts

Release date:	September 2022
Developer:	Gabriele Wach & Martin Gerner
Game type:	Hybrid
Number of players:	12–40
Format:	Hybrid
Time frame:	120–240 minutes
Languages:	English, German
Environment:	Preferably a third learning space with at least two generously sized rooms, ideally with a connection to wood or nature; Wi-Fi required for app use
Material:	Simulation-game kit with extensive materials (for forest managers and customers), shared and provided within a tandem facilitation setting
Price:	The game involves costs. An expense allowance is charged based on the duration, number of players, and scale (number of runs); materials are provided at a materials fee. Freely accessible/playable within a tandem facilitation setting

Resonance & Criticism

The Carlowitz-Planspiel is an exploratory simulation format designed to experience and practice sustainability. It is primarily used in higher education and formative learning contexts. Players often show enjoyment and a strong willingness to engage. This behavior is likely attributable to the haptic elements, which can be experienced only through direct interaction; their apparent simplicity often proves both surprising and intuitively accessible to players.

Criticism occasionally notes that complex interrelationships are didactically simplified; however, this is inherent to the simulation-game format.

The Carlowitz-Planspiel is continually accompanied by research, particularly regarding the transformative impact of an event-driven game dynamic.

Game Principle & Process

In the land of “Arboreacarlo,” everything revolves around trees. As a forest manager, you decide how they are cultivated and traded. As a customer, you have the choice of which wood products you purchase. Your skill level is determined via an app on the marketplace for wood and wood products. This is also where it becomes apparent how well prepared you are for incoming events. Will your tree species withstand a storm without damage? Which timber distributor gives you a clear conscience? Which wood products do you prefer? According to which criteria do you select them?

The Carlowitz-Planspiel is a turn-based format that makes self-efficacy in sustainable action tangible. Players test selected mechanisms of sustainable forestry from different perspectives, guided by selectable scenarios. Core didactic principles – informing, planning, deciding, implementing, monitoring, and evaluating – are central. Social interaction is integral to the gaming experience.

The Carlowitz-Planspiel is based on a purely qualitative, interactive scenario model; digital elements (app) are on an equal footing with haptic components. In addition to the German standard version, an international English-language version is available. The Carlowitz-Planspiel is moderated by a tandem of facilitators with subject-matter expertise and methodological-didactic training.

Game objectives become tangible step by step and are made explicit. Success results from round outcomes, integrated performance curves, and moderated exchange. Returns and payouts encourage creative competition and enable diverse strategic approaches. Interfaces with evidence and impact are embedded in the research design and are continuously explored.

The game design is based on interactionist stakeholder models, including principal–agent theory, decision dilemma models, and theories of distribution, scarcity, and justice (Rawls, 2024).

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

Through gameplay, sustainability becomes concrete, experiential, and activating, shifting from an abstract concept to a practical application across the forest, forestry, and timber industries, as viewed from changing perspectives. Players discover the interfaces between timber production and processing. They understand interactions between forest managers and customers and can empathetically assume both roles. They identify ecological, economic, and social sustainability variables and combine them into viable business and consumption models. In doing so, communication and cooperation pathways are used strategically and

autonomously to achieve goals. Players evaluate their performance according to sustainability criteria and examine how resources can be used economically and deployed in a future-oriented manner.

The following competencies are addressed: Subject-specific competencies focus on mathematics (calculation, estimation), economics (market mechanisms, supply and demand, consumer behavior, intermediaries), forestry, business model development, and biology (forest botany, tree growth, cultivation forms, uses, damage events). Methodological competencies include applying simulation game didactics, researching topics and preparing them in a user-oriented way, developing role profiles, thinking strategically, planning in a process-oriented manner, arguing creatively, negotiating purposefully, and organizing effectively. Social and communicative competencies include collaborating in teams, presenting, tolerating frustration, remaining open to criticism, regulating emotions, discussing spontaneously and eloquently, making decisions, prioritizing, and evaluating. Action-oriented competencies include fine motor skills in haptic handling (cutting, painting, assembling) as well as goal-oriented use of digital media (app).

Effectiveness

So far, no empirical studies on the effectiveness of the simulation game are available. Accompanying research on the effectiveness of the Carlowitz-Planspiel focuses on transformational aspects of players' behavior and actions (Gerner, 2022; Gerner, 2023). The resulting considerations and insights are regularly discussed with expert audiences and directly incorporated into the research design. Game progressions and round results are documented qualitatively (participant observation, wiki) and quantitatively (datasets, graphical processing), making them optimally usable for concrete reference during debriefing. In the future, the recording and evaluation system is intended to enable scientific assessment as well.

The research objective is to contribute to competency development through the Carlowitz-Planspiel, drawing on Brundiers et al. (2021), who propose a reference framework for key sustainability competencies in higher education (Sustainability Science, 16(1), 13–29). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-020-00838-2>.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

Game intention: Addressing sustainability without limiting game options. On the one hand, simulation-game principles and the Beutelsbach Consensus require opening up option spaces during gameplay rather than intervening in a manipulative or overwhelming manner (cf. Federal Agency for Civic Education, 2025). On the other hand, it is an explicit normative learning objective to become familiar with and experiment with sustainable game strategies.

Game haptics: Supporting transformative learning through haptic experience. Access through manual, tangible activities across all target groups fosters creative resonance and enables open, engaged engagement with sustainability issues.

Game context: Creating connectivity through added value. Adapting to changing conditions opens up diverse access points; the boundaries between formal, non-formal, and informal educational contexts often blur. The aim is to strategically leverage a broad range of points of reference with complementary added values, without risking arbitrariness.

Reviewer(s): Johannes Katsarov

Sources

Bundeszentrale für politische Bildung (2025). Beutelsbacher Konsens. In: Bundeszentrale für politische Bildung, 21.01.2025. Online verfügbar unter <https://www.bpb.de/die-bpb/ueber-uns/auftrag/51310/beutelsbacher-konsens/>, zuletzt geprüft am 01.08.2025.

Gerner, M. (2023). Sustainability through Simulation Games? Towards Designing a Research Agenda for Transformational Learning. In N. Becu (Ed.), Proceedings of the 54th Conference of the International Simulation and Gaming Association. Simulation and Gaming for Social and Environmental Transitions. International Simulation and Gaming Association (ISAGA) (pp. 10–19). La Rochelle: La Rochelle Université (ULR).

Gerner, M. (2022). The Art of Facilitating the Undesired. In T. Alf, S. Hahn, B. Zürn, & F. Trautwein (Eds.), ZMS-Schriftenreihe: Band 13. Planspiele - Erkenntnisse aus Praxis und Forschung: Rückblick auf den Deutschen Planspielpreis und das Europäische Planspielforum 2021 (pp. 29–46). Norderstedt: Books on Demand.

Rawls, John (2024): Eine Theorie der Gerechtigkeit. Unter Mitarbeit von Hermann Vetter. 24. Auflage. Frankfurt am Main: Suhrkamp (Suhrkamp-Taschenbuch Wissenschaft, 271).